

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The influence of husband's support on the psychological adaptation of postpartum mothers: A literature review

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Abstract

Introduction: After childbirth, postpartum mothers experience significant role changes, transitioning from being a wife to a mother responsible for child-rearing. This change requires adaptation to new identities and social roles, which can lead to emotional stress. If not addressed, this stress can result in psychological disorders such as stress, anxiety, or depression, especially in primiparous mothers who tend to be more anxious than multiparous mothers. Social support, particularly from husbands, is crucial in helping primiparous mothers face these challenges, although many husbands are unable to provide optimal support due to work commitments. Various studies have shown that husband's support can contribute to the psychological adaptation success of postpartum mothers.

Method: This study is a literature review, drawing from sources in Google Scholar, PUBMED, and Science Direct, focusing on research published between 2019 and 2024. The study included only original research articles in English or Indonesian with all the required components.

Result and Discussion: From the literature search, 10 studies met the inclusion criteria. Among them, 10 studies found an influence between husband support on the psychological adaptation success of postpartum mothers.

Conclusion: According to reviews, Husband's support influences the success of psychological adaptation in postpartum mothers.

Keywords: Husband support; Postpartum Mothers; Postpartum adaptation; Psychological adaptation; Psychological disorders

1. Introduction

Psychological adaptation during the postpartum period refers to the process through, adjust to the emotional and psychological changes associated with childbirth and the transition into motherhood. This period is often marked by significant shifts in a woman's life, including changes in identity, social roles, and daily routines. For primiparous mothers, these adjustments can be particularly challenging, as they are learning to navigate the responsibilities of caring for a newborn while coping with physical recovery from childbirth and hormonal changes (1). In multiparous women, the events of childbirth, hormonal changes, and baby care are experiences that should have been adapted to, while for primiparous women, it is the first experience that is considered very stressful (2).

Psychological changes in postpartum mothers can vary greatly from one individual to another, but there are some common changes that are often experienced. In mothers who successfully adapt, they will feel enthusiastic about caring for their baby. However, in mothers who are unable to adapt and experience psychological disorders, such as feeling

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sad, irritable, tired, angry, and hopeless, these feelings make them reluctant to take care of their baby (3). If the psychological adaptation process of the mother does not proceed well, it may lead to problems or psychological disorders during the postpartum period, such as postpartum blues or other psychological issues (4). In the psychological adaptation process of postpartum mothers, social support plays a crucial or vital role, especially support from close individuals. In a study conducted by Rut et al. (2013), it was stated that a lack of social involvement by the mother can lead to depression, which disrupts the mother's ability to achieve her developmental goals and fulfill her responsibilities and role as a mother (5). Therefore, support from the partner, family, and healthcare professionals will play an important role in helping the mother through the adaptation process during the postpartum period.

The husband is the person who is physically and emotionally closest to the wife or mother during pregnancy and childbirth, making him play a crucial role in providing support to his wife or mother during pregnancy and postpartum. The husband is the first person who can give attention and support to the wife or mother, offering love and making her feel protected both physically and emotionally (6). Husband's support during the postpartum period is a critical factor for primiparous mothers in coping with the psychological changes that occur, as a lack of support from the husband can negatively impact their adaptation to the postpartum period (7). Emotional, practical, and social support from husbands can help mothers overcome psychological challenges that may arise, such as postpartum blues or postpartum depression, while also accelerating physical recovery and psychosocial adaptation.

The lack of husband's support for mothers during the postpartum period can make them feel neglected and stressed. If this stress is prolonged, it may lead to the mother experiencing further stress, resulting in negative attitudes and undesirable behaviors, such as refusing to eat, avoiding medical check-ups, and negatively impacting her overall health. If this condition occurs, postpartum mothers are highly likely to experience various problems or complications, both physical and psychological, as a consequence of their inability to adapt during the postpartum period (8). Husband who are actively involved in child-rearing and household responsibilities help alleviate the emotional and physical burdens faced by mothers, thus improving their ability to adjust psychologically. Additionally, the emotional and practical support from a partner is associated with higher levels of maternal self-esteem and a greater sense of confidence in their ability to care for their newborn (9).

According to WHO (2022), Husband's support has several dimensions, including instrumental support, emotional support, esteem support, and informational support. One of the husband's roles within the family is to maintain the health of his wife after childbirth by showing love and care to make her feel appreciated, accompanying her for medical check-ups, encouraging her to eat nutritious food, get sufficient rest, maintain personal hygiene, and providing esteem support in the form of praise or positive feedback to the postpartum mother. Instrumental support includes helping with baby care (10).

This study aims to analyze the influence of husband's support on the psychological adaptation success of postpartum mothers. The goal is to enhance the understanding of the influence of husband's support on the success of psychological adaptation in postpartum mothers. Raising awareness about this condition is essential for reducing its impact on postpartum mothers' physical and psychological well-being, ensuring their overall quality of life.

2. Material and methods

This article is a literature review that examines 10 selected articles based on certain inclusion criteria. The selected articles present original research findings on the relationship between the influence of husband's support on the psychological adaptation of postpartum mothers. Articles were published between 2019 and 2024 (in the last five years) and in English or Indonesian. Exclusion criteria were applied to all articles discussing knowledge in relation to personal hygiene during menstruation using methods other than original research. Articles were sourced from several basic data, including Google Scholar, PUBMED, and Science Direct. Each article displayed will be analyzed descriptively, which includes the author and year of publication, research location, research method, research subject, and summary of research findings.

3. Results

Ten articles— seven in Indonesian and three in English—have been reviewed and analyzed as follows.

Table 1 Results of Review of 10 Articles

No	Author	Research Title	Location	Method	Subject	Result
1	Ariani, N.K.S., <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Dukungan Suami Dengan Proses Adaptasi Psikologi Pada Ibu Nifas RSAD Denpasar Bali	RSAD Denpasar, Bali, Indonesia	Analytical observational with a cross sectional approach. And sampling was using total sampling.	50 postpartum mothers at RSAD Denpasar Bali.	The majority of postpartum mothers who had good husband support, namely 22 (38.8%), experienced a safe and smooth taking-in phase, 14 (13.6%). 9 postpartum mothers who had less husband support (20%) experienced the taking in phase with post-partum blues as many as three people. Meanwhile, the results of hypothesis testing obtained a sig value of 0.000 (sig < 0.05). This means that there is a significant relationship between husband's support and the psychological adaptation process of postpartum mothers at RSAD Denpasar Bali.
2	Kusumastuti, A., <i>et al.</i> (2024).	Pengaruh Dukungan Suami Terhadap Proses Adaptasi Fisik dan Psikologis Ibu Nifas	TPMB Jakarta, Indonesia	Quantitative with cross sectional approach.	50 respondents who were postpartum mothers on days 7 to 14	Respondents' ability to adapt physically during the postpartum period, there were still 5 respondents (14%) who experienced poor physical adaptation. Psychologically, there were 7 respondents (14%) who experienced anxiety during the postpartum period. The husband's support felt by postpartum mothers fell into the poor category felt by the majority of respondents, namely 27 respondents (54%). The results of the research show that there is a significant relationship between husband's support and physical and psychological adaptation in postpartum mothers, with a p-value 0,03 (<0.05)
3	Putri, I, A., <i>et al.</i> (2021).	Penyesuaian Diri dan Dukungan Sosial Suami Dengan Baby Blues Syndrome Pada Ibu Primipara	Wilayah kerja Puskesmas Sumberrejo, Bojonegoro, Jawa Timur, Indonesia.	Quantitative correlations.	40 primiparous postpartum mothers with a duration of 3-14 days after giving birth.	Based on research results, the relationship between BBS and self-adjustment has a significance p value of 0.000 (p<0.005). This matter shows that there is a linear relationship between BBS and adjustment self, and the relationship between BBS and Husband's social support has a significance value of 0.000 (p<0.005). This matter shows that there is a linear relationship between BBS and support husband's social. Based on the R Square table, it can be seen that the R Square value is 92.3%. This proves that there is a strong relationship between self-adjustment and Social support of husbands with Baby Blues Syndrome in postpartum mothers primiparas in the working area of the Sumberrejo Community Health Center.

4	Ismiyanti, H. A., <i>et al.</i> (2023).	Dukungan Suami Pada Proses Adaptasi Psikologi Ibu Nifas	Puskesmas Tawiri, Maluku, Indonesia.	Case study	Mrs. M	In the case of Mrs. M during the first visit, which was on the third day postpartum, this period is known as the taking hold phase. During this period, Mrs. M received little support from her husband. There are many factors contributing to the lack of support from her husband, including his insensitivity to what his wife is experiencing, his busyness with work, and the persistence of traditional beliefs where the husband still considers child-rearing to be solely the wife's responsibility. As a result, Mrs. M expressed feelings of disappointment with her situation and a lack of motivation in caring for her baby
5	Takdir, M., <i>et al.</i> (2022).	Hubungan Dukungan Suami Terhadap Depresi Postpartum Ibu Nifas	Wilayah Kerja Puskesmas Bantimurung Maros, Sulawesi Selatan, Indonesia	Cross-sectional method with a descriptive analytical research design	35 postpartum mothers	After conducting research on 35 respondents to determine the relationship between husband support and postpartum depression, it was found that 10 respondents did not receive support, 19 respondents received adequate support, and 4 respondents received support. The Chi-Square test yielded a p-value of 0.04, indicating that the p-value is less than the alpha level of 0.05, which means that the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected. This indicates that there is an influence of husband support on postpartum depression in the working area of the Bantimurung Maros Health Center.
6	Komariah, K. (2024).	Hubungan Perubahan Psikologis Pada Ibu Postpartum, Dukungan Suami, dan Dukungan Bidan Dengan Kejadian Baby Blues di TPMB Siti Asiah Bekasi Tahun 2023	TPMB Siti Asiah, Bekasi, Indonesia.	Descriptive analysis with cross sectional approach.	54 postpartum mothers.	The results of the Chi-squared statistical test show a P-value of 0.019, where the P-value < α (0.05), indicating that there is a significant relationship between husband's support and the occurrence of baby blues at TPMB Siti Asiah Bekasi in 2023. The Odds Ratio is 4.950, meaning that respondents who received support from their husbands have a 4 times higher chance of not experiencing baby blues compared to respondents who did not receive support from their husbands.
7	Rahayu, S, F., <i>et al.</i> (2023).	Hubungan Dukungan Suami Dengan Terjadinya Postpartum Blues Pada Ibu Nifas	Wilayah Kerja Puskesmas Tempursari, Lumajang, Jawa Timur, Indonesia.	Observational with cross sectional design.	32 postpartum mothers.	The result of the cross-tabulation between spousal support and the occurrence of postpartum blues in postpartum mothers shows that the majority of postpartum mothers who experienced postpartum blues did not receive spousal support, with 17 individuals (53.2%). The result of the statistical test using the chi-square test with a p-value of 0.000 shows a significant value, p-value < α = 0.05, meaning that the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected. This indicates that there is a relationship between spousal support and the

						occurrence of postpartum blues in postpartum women in the working area of Tempursari Health Center in 2022.
8	Pebryatie, E., <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Associations Between Spousal Relationship, Husband Involvement, and Postpartum Depression Among Postpartum Mothers in West Java, Indonesia	27 independent midwifery clinics in 7 regions of West Java Province, Indonesia	cross-sectional study.	336 postpartum mothers who visited an independent midwifery clinic for postpartum care from November 2019 to January 2020.	The results indicate that the spousal relationship was significantly and positively associated with husband involvement ($\gamma = .60, P < .001$). Husband involvement was significantly and positively associated with maternal healthy behavior ($\gamma = .015, P < .001$) and negatively associated with postpartum depression ($\gamma = -.21, P < .001$). Husband involvement was also found to have an indirect influence on postpartum depression through maternal healthy behavior. In addition, family income was positively associated with the spousal relationship ($\beta = .15, P < .001$) while number of children was negatively associated with the spousal relationship and postpartum depression ($\beta = -.14, P < .001$ and $\beta = -.17, P < .001$, respectively). Spousal relationship, husband involvement, maternal healthy behavior, family income, and number of children, together predicted 13% of the variance in postpartum depression ($R^2 = .13$).
9	Ahmadpour, P., <i>et al.</i> (2021).	Family and Spousal Support Are Associated with Higher Levels of Maternal Functioning in a Study of Iranian Postpartum Women	Health centers of Tabriz, Iran	Quantitative with cross-sectional study.	564 women within one to four months after giving birth.	Results showed that t one-third of participants stated that they were receiving a high level of support from their spouses (39.5%) and family members (32.8%). The total score of maternal functioning in women with moderate (B: -4.44; 95% CI: -7.71 to -1.17; $p < 0.001$) and low (B: -4.77; 95% CI: -8.90 to -1.47; $p < 0.001$) spousal support was significantly lower compared to women who received a high level of spousal support. Additionally, this score in women with moderate (B: -5.22; 95% CI: -8.56 to -1.87; $p < 0.001$) and low (B: -3.90; 95% CI: -7.31 to -0.48; $p < 0.001$) family support was significantly lower compared to women who received a high level of family support. Study results suggest that receiving support from both a spouse and family members can improve maternal functioning.
10	Yaksi, N., & Save, D. (2021).	How do social and spousal support influence postpartum depression?	Family Health Centers (FHCs) in a district of Istanbul.	Cross sectional study.	303 mothers who gave birth in the last 6 months attending three FHCs.	The findings showed Low 'received social support' and spousal support scores but high 'unmet social support' was found to significantly increase Postpartum depression frequency. According to multivariate statistical analysis; while a higher income (OR : 0.99) and a higher spousal support score (OR: 0.95) were found as protective factors, actively working (OR :8.63), unplanned pregnancy

					(OR: 3.21), having a first child compared to having two children (OR: 11.20), having low birth weight infant (OR: 8.33) and unmet social support (OR: 1.02) were risk factors for PPD ($p < 0.05$).
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4. Discussion

4.1. The influence of husband's support on the psychological adaptation of postpartum mothers

Based on a review of 10 articles, all of them demonstrate a significant influence of spousal support on the success of psychological adaptation in postpartum mothers. These studies emphasize that the better the spousal support provided, the better the postpartum mothers will navigate the postpartum period.

The study with research Ariani et al, revealed that from 50 respondents, 22 (38.8%) postpartum mothers who received good support from their husbands experienced a smoother and safer psychological adaptation process during the taking-in phase. In contrast, among postpartum mothers who had less husband support, 9 individuals (20%) encountered difficulties in the taking-in phase, with 3 of them experiencing postpartum blues. This research confirms that husband's support has a crucial role in the success of the psychological adaptation process of postpartum mothers, especially in the taking-in phase ($P = 0,00$). Good support not only reduces the risk of psychological disorders but also increases the mother's chances of having a smoother postpartum period (11).

This study in line with research Kusumastuti, et al, regarding spousal support, the majority of respondents, specifically 27 (54%), felt that their husband's support was inadequate. The research findings indicate a significant relationship between the support provided by husbands and the physical and psychological adaptation of postpartum mothers, with a p-value of 0.03 (< 0.05), suggesting that increased husband's support is associated with better adaptation both physically and psychologically during the postpartum period (12).

Research by Putri et al, showed a significant relationship between Baby Blues Syndrome (BBS) and self-adjustment. This result suggests a linear relationship, meaning that as self-adjustment improves, the severity of BBS in postpartum mothers decreases. Additionally, the study found a similarly significant relationship between BBS and the social support provided by husbands, that higher levels of social support from husbands are associated with lower levels of BBS. If the social support from the husband to the postpartum mother is low, the likelihood of postpartum blues (BBS) is high. Conversely, if the social support from the husband to the postpartum mother is high, the likelihood of postpartum blues (BBS) is low (13). If the psychological adaptation process of the mother does not proceed well, it may lead to problems or psychological disorders during the postpartum period, such as postpartum blues or other psychological issues (4).

This study in line with research Ismiyanti et al, Mrs. M received little support from her husband, that cause Mrs. M expressed feelings of disappointment with her situation and a lack of motivation in caring for her baby (14). A lack of social involvement by the mother can lead to depression, which disrupts the mother's ability to achieve her developmental goals and fulfill her responsibilities and role as a mother (5). There are many factors that cause a lack of support from husbands, including husbands who are less sensitive to the conditions experienced by their wives, husbands being busy with work, still applying the old understanding where husbands still consider taking care of children as a wife's duty (14).

In a study conducted in Health centers of Tabriz, Iran, using a cross sectional study 564 women within one to four months after giving birth, a high level of support from their husband (39.5%) and family members (32.8%). The total score of maternal functioning in women with moderate (B: -4.44; 95% CI: -7.71 to -1.17; $p < 0.001$) and low (B: -4.77; 95% CI: -8.90 to -1.47; $p < 0.001$). The results of our study demonstrated that the mean total BIMF score was relatively high in the participants. The results of adjusted GLM also indicated that there was a statistically significant relationship between husband and family support level and sufficiency of income for expenses and maternal functioning (15). This study is in line with research Pebriyati et al, explained that husband involvement was significantly and positively associated with maternal healthy behavior ($\gamma = .015$, $P < .001$) and negatively associated with postpartum depression ($\gamma = -.21$, $P < .001$). Husband involvement was also found to have an indirect influence on postpartum depression through maternal healthy behavior. In addition, family income was positively associated with the spousal relationship (16).

In the study by research Takdir et al, after conducting research on 35 respondents to determine the relationship between husband support and postpartum depression, it was found that 10 respondents did not receive support, 19 respondents received adequate support, and 4 respondents received support. The results of the bivariate analysis indicate that there is an influence of husband support on postpartum depression in the working area of the Bantimurung Maros Health Center, with a p-value of $0.04 < 0.05$ (17). Postpartum mothers who receive sufficient support from their husbands during the psychological adaptation process during the postpartum period can reduce the risk of postpartum disorders. Postpartum mothers who received support from their husbands have a 4 times higher chance of not experiencing baby blues compared to postpartum mothers who did not receive support from their husbands (18).

In the study by Rahayu et al, on 32 postpartum mothers of Tempursari Community Health Center Working Area, Lumajang, the result of the cross-tabulation between spousal support and the occurrence of postpartum blues in postpartum mothers shows that the majority of postpartum mothers who experienced postpartum blues did not receive spousal support, with 17 individuals (53.2%). The statistical test using the chi-square test a significance of 0,000 with a (p-value < 0.05), this indicates that there is a relationship between spousal support and the occurrence of postpartum blues in postpartum women (19). Low received social support and spousal support scores but high unmet social support was found to significantly increase postpartum depression frequency (20). Sufficient husband support not only helps mothers face psychological challenges, but also contributes to mental health and overall family welfare because postpartum mothers are in good physical and psychological condition and husbands who understand about maternal and baby health can increase family harmony.

5. Conclusion

A review of ten journal articles revealed that most of them showed an association between the influence of husband's support on the psychological adaptation of postpartum mothers. Husband's support plays a big role in the successful psychological adaptation of postpartum mothers. Husband's support during the postpartum period is a critical factor for primiparous mothers in coping with the psychological changes that occur, as a lack of support from the husband can negatively impact their adaptation to the postpartum period, so husbands need to provide support both materially and emotionally. Husbands also need to be more understanding and understanding as the head of the household and as a partner, not to burden their wife too much with everything, and to be able to listen to their mother's concerns.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is one finding that contradict the theory.

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